

- V. K. BHAGWAT and R. V. SHANANE, *R sayanam*, 1939, 1, 191; *Chem. Abs.*, 1940, 34, 5070.
- H. SCHILDKNECHT and HANS SCHMIDT, *Z. Naturforsch.*, 1967, 22(3), 287-94.
- A. RUSSELL and H. C. GULLEDGE, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 64, 1313.
- A. R. L. DOHME, E. H. COX and E. MILLER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 48, 1691.
- D. B. LIMAYE and G. S. SHFNOLIKAR, *Rasayanam*, 1937, 1, 93; *Chem. Abs.*, 1938, 32, 2097.

Limiting Apparent Molal Volume of NaNO_3 and KNO_3 in Dioxane-Water Mixtures at Different Temperatures.

P. P. MISRA, N. C. DAS and P. B. DAS*

Department of Chemistry, S. C. S. College, Puri.

Manuscript received 12 May 1976, accep'd 15 January, 1977

THE variation of the limiting apparent molal volume (ϕ°) of electrolytes with temperatures have been employed to study ion solvent interaction by many workers both in aqueous and non-aqueous solutions, since it is the simplest thermodynamic property to measure¹⁻⁵. The variation of ' ϕ° ' with nonaqueous solvents is generally expressed on the basis of the weakening of the ion-dipole interaction energy. To have a more general idea about the behaviour of salts in nonaqueous solvents, the apparent molal volume ' ϕ° ' of NaNO_3 and KNO_3 in 10,20 and 30% dioxane-water mixtures at 30,35,40 and 45° have been calculated from the density data in the usual manner. The dioxane-water mixtures have been employed because of varying dielectric constants with a little tendency of hydrogen bonding.

In this present note, an attempt has been made to deal with the nature of the ion-solvent interaction of the salts in mixed solvents to see the effect of the dielectric constant, temperature and electrostriction on limiting apparent molal volume.

NaNO_3 and KNO_3 used were E. P. 'E. Merck' variety. The preparation of solvents, solutions and the measurements were the same as described by Prasad and coworkers⁶.

TABLE I— ϕ° VALUES

Salts	Temperature (°C)	10%D	20%D	30%D
NaNO_3	30	24.50	25.80	28.90
	35	27.24	29.81	31.33
	40	32.48	34.42	35.21
	45	36.31	38.80	40.41
KNO_3	30	30.74	32.48	35.91
	35	35.71	37.48	40.91
	40	40.58	41.45	45.48
	45	41.80	43.42	48.10

The ' ϕ° ' values for NaNO_3 and KNO_3 at 10,20 and 30% dioxane content and at different temperatures, evaluated in the usual manner³ are given in table I. The ' ϕ° ' values were found to be linear with temperature. The $d\phi^\circ/dt$ increases sharply with the increase in dioxane content in case of NaNO_3 but it is small in case of KNO_3 . This indicates that ion-solvent interaction is somewhat stronger in case of NaNO_3 and less in case of KNO_3 . This difference may be due to the release of solvent molecules loosely bonded to the K^+ ion and of the solvent molecules which may be accommodated inside the larger K^+ and are held by their weak vanderwaals forces.

Dioxane is more or less a nonhydrogen bonded solvent. So the ion-dipole interaction energy in absence of any hydrogen bond energy, would be appreciable and the attachment of the solvent molecules even to Na^+ and K^+ may not be loose; at the same time no structure formation would occur in the solvent around the ions⁷, as the dioxane content in the medium increases. The net result will be greater solvation. Now some solvent molecules will be associated with ions, while outside the ion-sphere, the solvent structure would almost be the same as that of the pure solvent and hence the expansion of the solution on heating would be comparatively less than that of the pure solvent and hence $d\phi^\circ/dt$ in case of NaNO_3 is sharp with increase in dioxane content. The attachment of solvent molecules is less in case of K^+ and hence $d\phi^\circ/dt$ does not change appreciably. Thus the variation of ' ϕ° ' with temperature appears to be satisfactorily explained by the concept of ion-solvent interaction and solvation.

It would be interesting to consider the electrostriction i.e. contraction of the solvent molecules in presence of electrolytes by comparing the limiting apparent molal volume of different dielectric constant. An increasing trend of ' ϕ° ' values with decrease in dielectric constant is very much noticeable. High dielectric constant would lower the electrostatic attraction of the ions on the solvent molecules resulting in a smaller contraction of the solvent. Hence in the present case, increasing trend of ' ϕ° ' with decrease in dielectric constant, suggests some contraction in the solvents.

Another interesting fact to which attention may now be drawn is that in the difference in ' ϕ° ' values of NaNO_3 - KNO_3 in solvents considered for the present communication is around 5-8 ml/mole and is almost independent of temperature. This difference i.e. 5-8 ml/mole does not correspond to the difference in the intrinsic volume of the ions obtained from the relation $4/3\pi r^3 N$, where 'r' being the radius of the ion in question as given by Robinson and Stokes⁸. This difference arises due to electrostriction or contraction in the solvents.

References

- W. R. BOUSEFIELD and T.R. LOWERY, *Trans. Farad. Soc.*, 1910, 6, 85.

- W. GEFFECKEN, *Z. Physik. Chem.*, 1931, A155, 1.
- A. F. SCOTT, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1931, 35, 2315.
- O. REDLICH and H. KLINGER, *Monatsch*, 1934, 65, 137.
- A. J. ELLIS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, (A), 1966, 1582.
- M. K. SRINIVASAN and B. PRASAD, *Trans. Farad. Soc.*, 1939, 35, 1442.
- R. GOPAL and P. P. RASTOGI, *Z. Physik. Chem.*, (N.F.), 1969, 67, 122.
- R. A. ROBINSON and R. H. STOKES, "Electrolyte Solutions", Butterworth Publishing Company, London, 1959, p. 124.

Quantum Chemical Calculations on A Dopamine Derivative

SEPHALI GUHA

Saha Institute of Nuclear Physics, C and MB Division,
92, Acharya Prafulla Chandra Road, Calcutta-9, India

Manuscript received 20 February, 1976, revised 1 December 1976, accepted 20 January 1977

A semi rigorous calculation by CNDO/2 method¹ is presented on the minimum energy conformation of protonated 5-hydroxy dopamine (5-HDA). 5-HDA (Fig. 1) has been shown to be a new 'false' sympathetic transmitter². The theoretical conformation of this molecule has been studied recently³ by the PCIO method⁴.

Fig. 1

Fig. 1. The (nonstandard) numbering system used for 5-hydroxydopamine molecule.

Fig. 2. 5-Hydroxydopamine: gross atomic populations--CNDO/2 and PCIO (within the parentheses).

The starting atomic coordinates were taken from crystallographic data⁵ and the total molecular energy for various conformations was calculated by allowing rotations around C1-C7 and C7-C8 bonds respectively. The torsion angles at the minimum energy conformation are found to be :

$$\tau_1 (C6-C1-C7-C8) = 56^\circ$$

$$\tau_2 (C1-C7-C8-N^+) = 40^\circ$$

There are 60 valence electrons in this molecule and the electronic energy of 5-HDA converged in 7 iterations to -529.5486 a. u. ($E_{\text{total}} = -131.9389$ a. u.). The gross atomic populations in the CNDO method are the diagonal elements of the density matrix where the density matrix is defined as the sum of the squares of the coefficients C_{ri} times the occupation numbers of each MO ϕ_i summed over the basis atomic orbitals χ_r . These are presented in Fig. 2.

As a result of the zero differential overlap approximation, one cannot calculate a quantity formally analogous to a total overlap population by the CNDO method. It has been shown⁶ that one can use the off-diagonal elements, scaled appropriately, in a Mulliken population analysis to obtain an approximation to total overlap populations. These results are shown in Table 1 for the atoms which can be considered as bonded to one another. It is to be noted that these TOPs seem to be of the correct magnitude for bonded atoms and that all the figures for TOPs between bonded atoms are large, of the order of 0.95 for C-C bonds or 0.6 to 0.7 for C to an external substituent atom. TOPs between non-bonded atoms are only of the order of 0.001.

Total overlap populations are of great potential interest for conformational studies. It has been shown that the maximum of the index molecular total overlap population (the sum of all the total overlap population in a molecule) is usually a more sensitive criterion of the equilibrium geometry than the minimum of the calculated total energy, especially for less than *ab initio* molecular orbital calculations^{7,8}. This index turns out to be especially significant for large molecules⁷. MTOPs have been proved to be useful in predicting equilibrium geometries. The MTOP for the minimum